

BABY FACTORIES AND CHILD ABUSE IN AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The rising cases of baby factories are the latest disturbing trend of child rights abuse in Nigeria. This issue is one of the social problems bedevilling our society due to poverty as the main factor that brings about the proliferation of baby factories as one of the most lucrative organized crimes across cities in Nigeria. Governments at all levels are combating this crime against humanity but people are still engaging in it as a business. This paper examined the patterns, trends and socio-economic factors that facilitate baby factories in Nigeria. This study adopted a survey design. 150 respondents were selected across the three senatorial districts of Akwa Ibom State using multiple sampling techniques, these include purposive, snowball and simple random sampling techniques. Primary data were collected through interview method and participant observation from security agencies such as the police, the prison, the court as well as the mass media were used analysis. Secondary data were collected through extant literature. Both primary and secondary data were analysed descriptively to draw conclusions and make recommendations. The paper utilized objectification theory as the framework for its analysis. Findings show that baby factories produced and sold babies for national or international adoption, rituals, slave labour and sexual exploitation. The paper recommends the prosecution of baby factory owners and workers to serve as a deterrence, a police toll-free call line should be given to the public to provide useful information to the police.

KEYWORDS: Baby Factories, Child Abuse, Surrogacy, and Child Right

INTRODUCTION

Nationally, child trafficking has formed the basis of organized crime against humanity. Nigeria is a developing country that is currently facing a series of social problems ranging from poverty, unemployment, and insecurity among others. People are engaging in any available

means for survival not minding the legality of such business. There are prevalent cases of baby factories and child trafficking in South-South geo-political zones, such as Uyo, Calabar, Yenogoa, Port Harcourt, Asaba, Benin and across other cities in Nigeria. Particularly in Akwa Ibom State, there are pending cases of baby factories and child trafficking in courts as a measure set aside by federal, state and local governments in combating this menace. Child abuse assumed a worrisome dimension with alarming growth in records of baby factories and child trafficking jointly affecting our society. Akwara and Andeshi (2014) stated that the various measures that appear very formidable and proactive thus failed to stamp out abuse of innocent children and the Nigerian government failed to effectively enforce similar workable measures to protect the rights of every Nigerian child against abuse as applicable in other developed countries of the world.

From my observation, cases of baby factories, child theft and child trafficking are always linked to popular politicians, business moguls and top bureaucrats who wish to serve as surrogate mothers or fathers, while others may wish to use these children for spiritual sacrifice to appease their gods for election success, promotion in workplace and protection. The government should make birth registration compulsory both in government hospitals and all those traditional birth attendants should register with the government and have a licence that could be retrieved from them if they are caught in buying and selling of babies. Religious leaders should caution against social stigma humiliation placed on unmarried teenagers/women with unwanted pregnancies, stigma placed on children born outside wedlock, and stigma placed on infertility among couples with only girl or boy child/children. These are factors that motivate people to patronize baby factories to buy and sell babies (Onuoha, 2014).

Child rights protection issues require harmonized policies and programmes that would protect the rights of children, The government at all levels as well as every citizen must be involved to protect the rights of these innocent children. People in urban and rural areas are engaging in the baby factory business as the cheapest way of making money without stress either through buying and selling for profit or paying a man to impregnate women to sell the babies, upon delivery, a token would be given to the man and the woman as compensation for the transaction. The sharing formula is made according to the owner of the factor to ensure that he/she makes profits after all the necessary expenses. Observations have shown that most men and women working in baby factories are people who have been labelled witches and wizards by their respective families and thrown out of the house without any means of survival and they resort to engaging in this illegal business.

There are prevalent cases of child theft in public places such as schools, churches, mosques, hospitals, markets, and public events. It has become a social problem because it has affected a significant number of children in society both the rich and the poor are affected, most especially the vulnerable ones. Child theft is an organized crime that is usually carried out by a group of syndicates that play significant roles in achieving a successful operation that gives them happiness while leaving the victim's family in agony. Students in secondary schools and tertiary institutions are locked up in facilities used as "baby factories" allowing the owners of the place to take control over them until they give birth to babies that are subsequently sold to third parties. Pregnant teenagers or adult women with unwanted pregnancies approach doctors, nurses, hospitals or orphanages that subsequently take care of these girls and women during their pregnancies while searching for those who would buy the babies, most of these girls and

women are forced by their traffickers to give birth for illegal adoption, illicit transfer and non-return of children abroad.

In the findings, we discovered that baby factories buy and sell babies to the public without minding what they use those babies for. The Akwa Ibom State police command has closed down several baby factories across the state, one of such was in Afaha Itam in Itu Local Government Area. According to the Police Relation Officer (PRO) SP Odiko Macedon, all those arrested would be charged to court immediately after investigation to serve a deterrence to those engaging in these crimes against humanity, he said that the police are ready to make the state uncomfortable for these set of people. Investigations have shown that most of the children bought from these baby factories are later accused of witches and wizards by their surrogate parents and thrown out of the house exposing them to various abuse, such as street hawking, prostitution, theft, house help syndrome and also use as sex delivery machines in baby factories. In Akwa Ibom State, these sets of people are found in the popular "Ibom Plaza" in Uyo. Another strategic place where these children are found is the "Itam flyover" in the Uyo metropolis.

These children are taken from these places with the hope of having good jobs for survival but end up being used as sacrificial prey by desperate politicians and businessmen/women while others are recruited and used as sex toys and delivery machines in various baby factories across the state. Investigation has shown that some Doctors/Nurses working in government hospitals and private hospitals are agents/middlemen to baby factory owners, sending clients to them through referral and getting their share in cash after successful transactions, they do not accept cash transfers or bank deposit to avoid being implicated by other syndicates during police investigation.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Baby factories are the latest disturbing illegal business in Nigeria particularly in Akwa Ibom State. Baby factories are found across various local government areas of Akwa Ibom State, these have become or social problem because they affect a significant number of children in the state, especially the vulnerable ones. This is because it has been established that almost all the cases of buying and selling of babies are traced to socio-cultural factors such as infertility among couples or only girl child/children and effort made by unmarried teenagers and women who are pregnant and in their bid to hide their condition for fear of stigma, discrimination and rejection fell into the ready arms of baby factory operators engaging in this criminal enterprise Nwaka (2019).

Unfortunately, scholarly works existing on the causes of baby factories failed to point out the sociocultural factors influencing such but centred mainly on economic problems such as poverty and unemployment as the main factors influencing the rise of baby factories into one of the most lucrative organized crime in Akwa Ibom State and Nigeria in general. The fight against this crime should not be left to the government alone, rather it should be a collective fight. The general public should provide useful information to the police through their call lines.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objective of the study is to investigate the socio-cultural and economic factors influencing the rise of baby factories in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

- i. To investigate the socio-cultural and economic factors influencing the rise of baby factories in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.
- ii. To examine the efforts made by the government and the public to reduce this crime.
- iii. To make some policy recommendations to the government on how to reduce the menace of baby factories.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The phenomenon of baby factories as a new trend in human trafficking is bedeviling Nigeria and has thus posed issues of child abuse in recent times. Baby factories mostly thrive due to some socio-cultural and economic factors, some societies are structured patriarchal, thereby making it mandatory for each family to have a male child. In a situation where there are only girls/children, such families resort to buying a male child from a baby factory. Infertility is another factor that forced families to patronise baby factories just to avoid social stigma Onuoha (2014). Thus, there is a need for preventing and responding to violence, exploitation and social stigma placed on unmarried teenagers/women with unwanted pregnancies, stigma placed on children born outside wedlock, stigma placed among couples or couples with only girl child/children are the socio-cultural factors influencing this criminal enterprise trading in buying and selling of babies. However, economic factors that give rise to baby factories are attributed to poverty, unemployment and economic hardship, corruption, illiteracy and lack of information, and trafficking Huntley (2013). However, while scholars like Ojedokun and Atoi (2012) concentrated move on economic factors, few works pointed out some cultural factors that gave rise to baby factories. For instance, Onuoha (2014) made a strong point for cultural factors that promote the rise of baby factories such as; the premium placed on having a biological child, infertility and the cultural practice of Ostracizing pregnancies out of wedlock. Huntley (2013) also mentioned gender discrimination and social stigmas in Nigerian society as some causal factors. Furthermore, scholars like Kanu (2014), added that children are being produced in baby factories mostly for crime-laden, international country adoption systems for customers in Europe and America from African countries such as Nigeria, Namibia, Ghana, Benin Republic, Gabon and Ethiopia.

Efforts were made by the government to reduce the menace of baby factories. Presently, the phenomenon of baby factory business and child abuse cuts across the various zones in Nigeria though it is more prevalent in the southern state, appearing rampant in Abia, Akwa Ibom, Cross River, Imo, Rivers and Anambra. It has also been reported in Benue, Lagos, Ogun and Ondo, Onuoha (2014). Some baby factories were discovered in various states of Nigeria as outlined; and reported in PM News, (2013) and Punch (2013)

- i. In 2011, the police raided two hospitals and dismantled two baby factories in Enugu State.
- ii. In June 2011, 32 pregnant girls were rescued in Aba, Abia State from a hospital of the Cross Foundation.
- iii. Between January and March 2010, 77 girls were rescued in other parts of Abia State.
- iv. In 2007, 19 girls were rescued from a cartel that operated between Aba and Port Harcourt in Rivers State.

Although the Phenomenon of the baby factories in Nigeria is relatively new in its recognition as the worst form of crime against humanity it is necessary for the perpetrators of this crime against vulnerable infants shortly after their birth into this world to be fished out as a

state of emergency and be severally punished to serve as deterrence to others engaging in this booming, but brutal business. This is in line with another interview with a founder of one of the popular orphanages in Nigeria which threw new light into what may be the reason for the high incidence of baby factors where she reportedly said that the desire of Nigerians to make quick money and also to adopt babies appear to be the factors in the increasing rate of crime (Kanu, 2014).

Government at all levels should organize nationwide public awareness campaigns to educate citizens and law enforcement operatives about the phenomenon of baby factories and human trafficking to warn parents about new trends in children and new schemes used by these people to lure their victims and to spite communities to participate in the fight against the baby factory. Awareness should be made to include meetings with citizens at town halls, schools, and churches, dissemination of advocacy materials and media appearances. The government should enforce the Child Rights Act to ensure that vulnerable children are protected against abuse Akwara (2014).

The government should give out financial rewards to informants who would volunteer information about baby factory operators and syndicates. The government should implement clear-cut rules about punishments for arrested baby factory syndicates and defaulters. Childbearing and protection are the responsibility of the family and the society, Nigeria is a pro-natalist society. If lays much emphasis on childbearing and child protection is seen as a definition of womanhood and manhood to ensure procreation Nwaka (2019).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The study adopts the objectification theory propounded by Frederickson and Robert (1970) to understand and explain the experience of girls and women in situations where their autonomy and humanity are negated through objectification (Calogero, 2012, P. 579). The epistemological foundation of the theory is traceable to modern studies in social psychology and feminism with themes of self-objectification gender violence and victimization as well as sexual objectification as cardinal influences (Balraji, 2015).

To meaningfully situate its theoretical application, the concept of objectification requires proper contextual clarification. For Calogero (2012, p. 574), objectivity simply means to make an object which can be used, manipulated, controlled and known through its physical properties. Concerning human beings, the essence of objectification is to deny a person his/her autonomy, agency and subjectivity (Nussbaum, 1995). Based on Nussbaum's (1995) conceptual frame, seven dimensions of objectification or possible: instrumentality, denial of autonomy, inertness, fungibility, viability, ownership and denial of subjectivity.

Objectification theory offers interesting insights into the extent of victimization associated with 'baby factories' in Nigeria. This includes the buying and selling of infants as commodities, the enslavement and exploitation of the surrogate mother, and the instrumentalization of young girls/women as reproductive machines as well as objects of trafficking (Guevara, 2017). Under these circumstances, the victims are not only commoditized but they are also dehumanized and victimized (Okoli 2019). As expendable objects, women in this context are stripped of their humanity, autonomy, agency and subjectivity (Gervais *et al.*, 2015). Even where their participation in the process is voluntary, they are ultimately cheated or exploited. In most instances, the baby bearer gets a reward of twenty thousand naira (equivalent to about 50 USD) for giving away her child (Obaji, 2020).

This amount translates roughly to the monthly gross earnings of an average Nigerian under-class artisan. So, even when they are being compensated for their role, what they get is usually not a fair and dignifying reward for the double labour, the dual reproductive and productive burden of commercial child-bearing. The foremost pattern of surrogacy in the world entails the man donating his sperm through organic insemination (direct sexual intercourse) to a surrogate who will bear the child (Nwak, 2019).

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a survey design. A total of 150 respondents were selected across the three Senatorial Districts of Akwa Ibom State using purposive, snowball and simple random sampling techniques. Primary data were obtained through interviews and participant observation. While secondary data were generated from extant literature. Primary were collected and analysed thematically with excerpts from study participants.

RESULT

Based on the objectives of this study, certain questions were asked to draw attention and accommodate the views of the various respondents who would give appropriate responses on the subject. The objective was to investigate the socio-cultural and economic factors influencing the rise of baby factories in Akwa Ibom State Nigeria. Objective two was to examine the efforts made by the government and the public to reduce the menace of baby factories. Objective three was to make some policy recommendations to the government. The respondents say that baby factories are mostly thriving due to some socio-cultural and economic factors, some societies are structured in a patriarchal manner, thereby making it mandatory for each family to have a male child, and the respondents say that in this situation such families resort to buying a male child from baby factories. The respondents further stated that another factor is infertility usually forces families to patronise baby factories just to avoid the social stigma of childlessness.

According to the respondents, economic factors that give rise to baby factories are attributed to poverty, unemployment, corruption, illiteracy and desperation to become rich overnight. The respondents say that our youths see baby factories as the fastest way of making money by selling their babies or engaging on the child making money by selling your babies or engaging in child theft where such babies are sold to baby factory operators. The respondents say that the government should organize nationwide public awareness campaigns to sensitize the citizens and law enforcement operatives about the new trend in child trafficking. The respondents also narrated the ordeal of these babies as most of them were used as sacrificial lambs by politicians, businessmen and women while some used them as sex toys.

In an interview with chief Edet Asuquo aged 60 years on the study participants said:

He said that the government have put all mercenaries on the ground to combat the menace of baby factories, including the police, the prison and the court to prosecute and convict any person(s) caught in this illegal business, Interviewed on 12-2-2024.

In an interview with the police public relations officer;

The force PPRO Odiko Macdon said that the baby factory business is illegal and the government have put everything in place to make

the operators of these factors uncomfortable. The PPRO said that men of the force are combat-ready to dislodge all baby factories in the state and prosecute all the culprits accordingly, interviewed on 10-2-2024.

The researcher while visiting one of the scenes of a baby factory invaded by police in Afaha Itam, Itu Local Government Area, observed that the nursing mothers were young girls from age 17 to 34 years who engaged in this business.

Gathered information through interviews and observation has shown that all the syndicates in the baby factory business were desperate for money. The youth leader of Afaha Itam Akparawa Essien Job said that he was shocked that such business was going on in his community (Essien, male, 48 years, interviewed on 8-2-2024).

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings from the study show that socio-cultural and economic factors influence the rise of baby factories, this is because most families are desperate to have a male child while others are also struggling for a female child. The study shows that economic factors like making money and becoming rich overnight force our youths and adults to be involved in the baby factory business. The study showed that infertility is another factor that forced families to patronise baby factories just to avoid social stigma (Onuoha, 2014). The study also shows that social stigma placed on unmarried teenagers/women with unwanted pregnancies forces them to sell their babies to baby factories and collect money as a reward. The study shows that stigma placed among children born outside wedlock also forces their mothers to sell their babies in baby factories to avoid being labelled as bastards. The findings from the study show that economic factors that give rise to baby factories are attributed to poverty, unemployment, corruption, illiteracy and lack of information on human trafficking (Huntley, 2013).

The findings show that some rich politicians' businessmen and women who need spiritual protection patronise baby factories where they buy babies used as sacrificial prey to the gods. The study also shows the efforts made by the government to reduce the menace of baby factories, these include a nationwide public awareness campaign to educate the citizens and law enforcement operatives about the phenomenon of baby factories and human trafficking to warn parents about new trends in child theft and the need protect against child abuse (Akwara, 2014).

Findings in the study have shown that socio-cultural and economic factors are influencing the rise of baby factories in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. It has also been revealed that the majority of these baby factories are using teenagers as sex reproductive machines just to reward them with a token after birth (Obaji, 2020). The study has shown the foremost pattern of surrogacy in the world entails the husband donating his sperm through organic insemination to a surrogate who will bear him the child instead of his infertile wife (Oyekan, 2017). This study has shown that families engaged in all these acts to avoid the social stigma of childlessness and the desperation of having a male child. It is sad as we have revealed that most babies bought from baby factories are used as sacrificial prey as shown in the appendix where a child was slaughtered. It has also been shown that the government have tried to eliminate the menace of the baby factory business in Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

The menace of baby factories in Nigeria is a profitable illegal business that poses a great challenge for the government to eradicate it. Nigeria has already undertaken several legislative and other measures to address the human trafficking problem within its borders. Underpinned by the logic of socio-existential and criminal opportunism, 'baby factories' in Akwa Ibom state, Nigeria have blossomed into a sort of a burgeoning underground enterprise, with pregnant girls and infants as stocks in trade.

The problem with the practice lies less in its tendency to commodification than in objectification, in some cases where babies are placed as collateral and abuses associated with it, the phenomenon has continued to thrive alongside its surrogate and adoptive practices. To mitigate the menace, it is pertinent to regularize the abusive practice through a proper surrogacy/child adoption regiment capable of regulating the associated practices and deterring abuses.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- i. The government should create employment opportunities for the people to reduce poverty which forces people to indulge in the baby factory business.
- ii. There is a need for nationwide orientation and sensitization through social services aimed at strengthening bonds within families, communities and the wider society to enhance the atmosphere of love, respect and safety for child protection.
- iii. Traditional rulers and other key stakeholders should provide useful information to the police concerning the activities of baby factories in their vicinity.

REFERENCES

- Andeshi, C. A. & Charles, A. Akwara (2014). Dialectics of the incubation of 'Baby factories' in Nigeria. *International Journal of Peace and Conflict Studies* (OJPCS), 2 (1): 82-90.
- Calogero, R. M. (2012). Objectification theory, Self-objectification and body image (p. 375-580).
- Ele, C. O. (2016). The proliferation of baby factories in Nigeria: An ethical perspective. *Online Journal of Arts, Management and Social Sciences*, 2(1), 82-90.
- Gervais S. J. Bernard, P. Klein, O., & Allen, J. (Eds.) (2013). Objectification and (de) humanization. Nebraska Symposium on motivation, 60.
- Guevara, L. E. & Albaran, E. S. (2017). Babies trafficking networks in the democratic republic of Congo and Nigeria Research Paper no 7. Bogota, Columbia. *The Global Observatory of Transnational Criminal Network*.
- Huntley, S. (2013). The phenomenon of "Baby Factories" in Nigeria is a new trend in human trafficking. *International Crime Database*. IVF brief 3.
- Kanu, A. (2014). Baby factories: New Face of Human Trafficking. In New Telegraph Sanctity of Truth.
- Makinde, O. A., Olaleye, O., Makinde, O. O., Hynley, S. S. and Brown, B. (2017). "Baby factories" in Nigeria: starting the discussion towards a national prevention policy. *Trauma, Violence and Abuse*, 18(1), 98-105.
- New Telegram (2023). NDLEA arrested five pregnant teenagers in a baby factory in Imo state, p. 6, September 18, 2023.
- Nwaka, J. C. and Odoemene, A. (2019). "Baby Factories" Exploitation of women in southern

- Nigeria. *Dignity: A Journal on Sexual Exploitation and Violence* 4 (2), 1-5.
- Nwaogugu, E. (2004). *Family law in Nigeria*. Ibadan: Heinemann Educational Books.
- Nwaolikpe, O. N. (2018). The Mass media and national development: The case of “Baby factory” activities in Nigeria. *International Journal of Arts and Humanities*, 7(1), 71-84.
- Obaji, P. (2020). Survivors of Nigeria's 'baby factories' share their stories. Aljazeera Features.
- Ojedokun, U. A and Atoi, E. N. (2012). The baby dumping phenomenon in Nigeria: A study on the perception of market women in Ibadan. *International Journal of Child Youth and Family Studies* 4(1): 409-425.
- Okolu, A. C. (2019). *Boko Haram Insurgency and gendered victimhood: Women as corporal victims and object of war* 30(6-7), 1214-1232.
- Onuoha, F. C. (2014). New wares of trade: Understanding evolving baby factory and trafficking in Nigeria. A paper presented at the 5th International Conference of the Institute of Security Studies, Johannesburg, South Africa. *National and International Perspectives on crime reduction and criminal Justice* 14-15 August 2014.
- PM News, (2013). 19 pregnant girls freed in Latest baby factory bust.
- Punch, (2013). *Baby Factory: Enugu Police Nab Hair Dresser, Lover*.
- Pyekan, A. O. and Ani A. E. (2017). Surrogacy and motherhood question in Yoruba Culture. *Bangladesh Journal of Bioethics* 8 (3), 26-2.